

The Evaluation of Health Benefits of Landscaping on Wellbeing of Landscapers in Sokoto South Local Government Area of Sokoto State, Nigeria

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This study examines the health benefits of landscaping on the well-being of landscapers in Sokoto South Local Government Area of Sokoto State, Nigeria. The research was motivated by the growing concern over the limited attention given to landscaping practices and their associated health benefits in residential environments within the study area. The study specifically aimed to describe the socio-economic characteristics of landscapers, assess the health benefits of landscaping, explore their perceptions toward landscaping practices, and identify the constraints affecting landscaping activities. A simple random sampling technique was used to select respondents, and primary data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to 30 landscapers. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage, while the chi-square test was employed to test the study hypothesis. The findings revealed that the majority of landscapers were young males with varying levels of educational attainment. Landscaping was found to contribute significantly to environmental improvement and human well-being through benefits such as temperature regulation, erosion control, air purification, and psychological relaxation. The study also showed that most respondents engaged in landscaping primarily for beautification and economic purposes. However, key constraints identified include high maintenance costs, land tenure insecurity, pest and disease challenges, and limited access to improved plant varieties. The chi-square analysis confirmed a significant relationship between landscaping and human health and well-being in the study area. Based on these findings, the study recommends increased awareness creation, government support, training programs, and improved access to resources to enhance sustainable landscaping practices. In conclusion, landscaping plays a vital role in improving environmental quality and promoting the overall well-being of individuals, and its adoption should be encouraged in both rural and urban communities.

Key Words: Evaluation, Health Benefits, Wellbeing, Landscapers, Sokoto South.

INTRODUCTION

An appealing landscape contributes to people's health (Abraham *et al.*, 2009). Studies prove that the environment surrounding a person is of great importance to his or her stress level and health. Various human activities produce pressures that alter the environment, leading to negative impacts on the human health and the

environmental eco-system (Barmelgy, 2013). Studies confirm that inhabitants could benefit from nature, greening and landscape through direct contact with such an environment. Greenery has the potential of inducing an active living and increasing public health (Barmelgy, 2013). Which aimed to promote landscape protection, management and planning, considers landscape as "a key element of individual and social well-being"?

The World Health Organization (2016) defined health as "Health, according to the World Health Organization, is

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"a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease and infirmity". A variety of definitions have been used for different purposes over time. Health can be promoted by encouraging healthful activities, such as regular physical exercise and adequate sleep. This understanding of landscape and health provides the background for our approach to investigating the evidence for the role of exposure to the visual landscapes for individual and social health and well-being. My definition of health effects reflects the broad health definition of the WHO, encompassing effects on physical, mental and social well-being. Society is facing increasing challenges with stress-related diseases, and knowledge about the way the visual landscape affects health and well-being can help mitigate stress and increase restoration. Links between landscape and health have been observed for a long time and in many different cultures and societies. The belief that viewing vegetation, water and other natural elements can ameliorate stress and is beneficial for patients in healthcare environments dates as far back as the earliest large cities in Persia, China and Greece. In the middle Ages, the first hospitals in Europe were infirmaries in monastic communities where a cloistered garden was an essential part of the environment used to bring relief to the ill (Ulrich, 2002).

A range of theories and approaches have been forwarded in order to explain and assess the influence of landscapes on human health. Contemporary theories, such as Ulrich's "Stress Recovery Theory" (Ulrich, 2002), predict that natural scenes tend to reduce stress, whereas settings in the built environment tend to hinder recovery from stress. Researchers have provided possible explanations for this relationship. Evolutionary theories of landscape preferences explain the benefits of natural scenes as reflecting landscape qualities that satisfy human biological needs. Researchers within environmental psychology have evaluated whether the restorative effect of natural landscapes is one of the reasons why people prefer natural landscapes over urban ones (Van den Berg *et al.*, 2017).

One of the research approaches relating to health effects of landscapes is known as "Healing Gardens". If the view from a hospital window is important in terms of improving recovery (Ulrich, 2007) then the design of hospital gardens becomes a new and significant topic. This topic has been investigated in recent studies of gardens and parks, particularly those around hospitals and residential areas. Such studies assess whether healing gardens aid restoration from stress and improve comfort and well-being (Sherman *et al.*, 2015).

"Restoration" has been defined as "the process of renewing physical, psychological and social capabilities diminished in ongoing efforts to meet adaptive demands", i.e. not only intentional (Hartig, 2014). Stephen and Kaplan (2019) examined the factors that make a restorative experience more likely. Natural environments

are thought to be especially effective as restorative settings, as they usually possess the key factors in achieving restoration. Kaplan (2002) describes the "Attention Restoration Theory" in terms of the central role of attention and attention fatigue in determining quality of life (Kaplan, 2022).

Another approach to studying health effects of landscapes relates to the concept "Therapeutic Landscapes". This is linked to the idea of place identity, and to the use of particular places for the maintenance of health and well-being. The concept was introduced at the beginning of the 1990s by the health/medical geographer Gesler (2005), who employed an expanded definition of the concept of landscape taken from cultural geography with the aim of exploring the positive, healing or therapeutic characteristics of place (Gesler, 2005).

The terms "healing" or "therapeutic" generally refer to a beneficial process that promotes overall well-being. According to Cooper-Marcus and Barnes (2015) they are used to describe either one or a mixture of the three following processes: relief from physical symptoms, illness or trauma (e.g., a recovering postoperative patient); stress reduction and increased levels of comfort for individuals dealing with emotionally and/or physically tiring experiences; and an improvement in the overall sense of well-being. The term "*therapeutic landscape*" has traditionally been used to describe landscapes with "enduring reputation for achieving physical, mental and spiritual healing" (Gesler, 2005). Research focused on places that had achieved this reputation for healing such as Lourdes, Bath or the Navajo territory (Gesler, 2008) but the concept is being adapted and expanded to cover not only healing places, but places that promote well-being and maintain health with the goal of analysing what it is that influences visitor experience (Palka, 2009).

Environmental perception is clearly multi-sensory, and not restricted to vision. However, vision is by far our most important sense in terms of yielding information about outdoor environments (Ulrich, 2007). A significant part of the satisfaction derived from nature does not require being in the natural setting, but rather having a view of it. Several studies that have shown health benefits related to experiencing nature have been based on opportunities for noticing and observing it, rather than on performing activities in nature (Kaplan, 2002).

The visible landscape features is believed to affect human being in many ways, including aesthetic appreciation, health, and well-being. This is given less priority in most household and building facilities in Sokoto South LGA Sokoto, as many residential houses within this area pay less priorities and attention to the health benefits of landscaping in their area. This has led to fewer information and awareness creation about the health effects contributions and benefits of landscaping as related to health and well-being of most natural environments and landscapers in the study area. Therefore, this research is to assess the Health Benefits

Figure 1: Map of Sokoto, Showing the Study Area

of Landscaping on Wellbeing of Landscapers in Sokoto South LGA, Sokoto State.

The research questions are;

- 1.What are the socio-economic characteristics of the landscapers in the study area?
- 2.What are the health benefits of landscaping to wellbeing of landscapers in the study area?
- 3.What is the perception of landscapers in Sokoto South LGA towards Landscaping practices of their environments?
- 4.What are the constraints faced by landscapers towards landscaping of their residential houses and areas in Sokoto South LGA, Sokoto State?

General objective of this research is to assess the Health Benefits of Landscaping on Wellbeing of Landscapers in Sokoto South LGA, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives of this research are to:

- 1.Describe the socio-economic characteristics of the landscapers in the study area.
- 2.Assess the health benefits of landscaping to wellbeing of landscapers in the study area.
- 3.Explore the perception of landscapers in Sokoto South LGA towards Landscaping of their environments.
- 4.Identify the constraints faced by landscapers towards landscaping of their residential houses and areas in Sokoto South LGA, Sokoto State.

The research hypothesis is;

There is significant relationship between Landscaping and human health & wellbeing.

This research will contribute to the literature and previous researches regarding the attributes of landscapes and its health benefits. The research approach will contribute to the theoretical basis for landscape design benefits to human health, and will also serve as a reference for further research on the relationship between different landscaping elements and patterns on human health and well-being. This research work focused on landscapers in their residential areas in Sokoto South Local government area of Sokoto State towards the landscaping and its health benefits on their wellbeing, this research will be limited to Sokoto South Local Government Area, Sokoto State due to the vast population and large size of Sokoto State and as well state of Insecurity which is also a limiting factor to this research.

METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

This research work was conducted at Sokoto South Local Government Area of Sokoto State. Sokoto South local government area is located in Sokoto state, North-west Nigeria. The headquarters of the LGA is in the town of Sokoto. The LGA falls within the Sudan Savannah and witnesses two distinct seasons which are the dry and the rainy seasons with the average wind speed putting at 11 km/h. Sokoto metropolis according to Koppen's classification the climate of the study area is classified as Hot Semi-arid climate (BSh). Sokoto state is in the dry Sahel with an annual average temperature of 28.3 °C, it is one of the hottest cities in the world. Maximum daytime temperatures are generally under 40°C most of the year,

Table 1. Distribution of landscapers according to their age.

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
15 – 20 years	0	0
21 – 30 years	11	36.7
31 – 40 years	8	26.7
41 – 50 years	6	20
51 and above	5	16.7
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

and the dryness makes the heat unbearable (Koppen, 2023). The dry season lasts for more than seven months, being particularly dry from mid-November to mid-May when no drop of rain may fall. The warmest months are February to April when daytime temperatures can exceed 45 °C. The rainy season is from June to October during which showers are a daily occurrence. The hot season lasts for 2.2 months, from March 17 to May 23, with an average daily high temperature above 101°F. The hottest month of the year in Sokoto is April, with an average high of 104°F and low of 80°F. The cool season lasts for 1.6 months, from December 10 to January 29, with an average daily high temperature below 91°F. The coldest month of the year in Sokoto is January, with an average low of 63°F and high of 89°F.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

Simple Randomized sampling technique was used to select some major districts within Sokoto South local government of Sokoto which includes: *Sarkin Zamfara, Dorowa, Gagi, Tudun Wada, Adar Kwanni, Dandi, Rujin Sambo, Rijiyar Dorowa, Mabera Idi, Salami and Mana*. Sample was chosen from the set of landscapers from the districts within the study area, due to large size of the target population, the sample size was determined through the use of Taro Yamane formula for estimation and sample size determination for population sampling as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size
N = the target population 50
e = margin of error (5%)

$$n = \frac{45}{1 + 45(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{45}{1 + 45(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{45}{1 + 0.51}$$

$$n = \frac{45}{1.51}$$

$$n = 30$$

Therefore, by this calculation, the sample size was 30.

Method of Data Collection

Data for the study were obtained from primary secondary sources respectively. However, the primary data was collected through the aid of structured questionnaire that was administered to the Landscapers which was used to collect the quantitative data for the study.

Instrument of the Study

A well structured questionnaire was used for collection of data for this study which was clearly designed with aid of questions to obtain, socio - economic characteristics of landscapers that are into landscaping as a business, and households within Sokoto South local government area of Sokoto.

Method of Data Analysis

Objectives 1,2 and 4 of these research was subjected to descriptive statistics in form of frequency percentage in a tabular form and Chi Square was used to test for objective 3 and to test for the hypothesis in response to the relationship between the health challenges and its contributions to well being of landscapers in the study area.

$$X^2 = \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where,

X^2 = Chi square value

O = Observed value

E = Expected value

RESULTS

SECTION A: Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Landscapers

Table 1 shows those 11 landscapers representing (36.7%) are between 21 – 30years old, 8 landscapers representing (26.7%) are between 31 – 40years old while 6 respondents representing (20%) shows the

Table 2. Distribution of Landscapers According to their Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	30	100
Female	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 3. Distribution of Landscapers according to their Religion.

Religion	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Islamic	30	100
Christianity	0	0
Traditional	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4. Distribution of Landscapers according to their Highest Qualifications.

Qualifications	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No formal Education	1	3.3
Quranic School	7	23.3
Primary School Leaving Certificate	5	16.7
Secondary School Leaving Certificate	6	20
Higher Institutions	11	36.7
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4. Distribution of Landscapers according to their Marital Status.

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	12	40
Married	13	43.3
Widow	5	16.7
Divorce	2	6.7
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

respondents that are 41 – 50years. 5 (16.7%) of the landscapers are recorded to be above 51years old and above. The highest range of respondents is between 21 – 30 years old which implies that younger people are into landscaping in the study area. This can be compared to their strength and capabilities of working and their strength in making landscaping a service in the study area. Table 2 shows that 30 of the landscapers are male, implies that 100% of the respondents are male, this can be traced or contrast to the fact that most men are into landscaping in the study area whereby most women are into others business activities most especially trading, in determining the concept of this study, 100% of the respondents are male.

Table 3 shows that 30 landscapers representing (100%) of the study are Muslims; this is related to the fact

that the study area is dominated by most Muslims and no Christians or other religion are into farming activities or residents of the study area.

Table 4 shows that majority of the Landscapers had higher institutional education with 11 Landscapers representing 36.7%, 7(23.3%) attends Quranic School education and Primary education with 5(16.7%) While only 1(3.3%) has no formal education. This implies that most of the Landscapers in the study area had acquired certificate of higher institutions. This can be attributed to the fact that majority of the Landscapers are young and landscaping practices is more acquiring of special trainings.

Table 5 shows Landscapers according to their marital status, 12(40%) of the Landscapers are single, while 13(43.3%) of the Landscapers are married,

Table 6. Distribution of Landscapers according to their Family Size.

Family Size	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 – 5	12	40
6 – 10	13	43.3
11 – 15	5	16.7
Above 15	2	6.7
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 7. Distribution of landscapers on how poor landscaping practices threatened the environmental health challenges in the study area?.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Water Logging	6	20
Erosion and Land Degradation	1	3.3
Overgrown Weeds and Grasses	15	50
Non Conducive Environment	8	26.7
Others	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 8. Distribution of landscapers on how description of poor facilities that evolves the poor landscaping planning of the study area.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Poor Source of Good Water	7	23.3
Poor Sanitation (Refuse Dumping)	9	30
Poor Defecating Site (Toilet)	10	33.3
Improvising of Conservable Vegetation for good living	4	13.3
Others	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

5(16.7%) of the Landscapers are widowed while the least is 2(6.7%) of the Landscapers who are divorcee. This implies that most of the Landscapers in the study area are married and are really into the landscaping practice in the study area.

Table 6 shows landscapers according to their family size, 12(40%) of the landscapers has between 1 – 5 in family size, while 13(43.3%) of the landscapers has between 6 – 10 numbered in family size, 5(16.7%) of the landscapers has between 11 – 15 in family size while the was 2(6.7%) of the landscapers who has above 15 in family size. This implies that most of the respondents are married and are having more dependents family size to consider in their well being.

SECTION B: Assess the Health Contributions of Landscaping to human well-being of landscapers in the Study Area.

Table 7 shows that 6(20%) of the landscapers responded that poor landscaping practice in the study areas has led to water logging while, 1(3.3%) of the landscapers

reported that poor landscaping has led their land to be washed off by erosion and has been degraded, 15(50%) of the landscapers reported that poor landscaping in the area has led to some areas to be covered with overgrown weeds and grasses while 8(26.7%) of the landscapers reported that poor landscaping has open the environment not to be conducive for residential purposes, this implies that but weather condition, infrastructures in the study area has been affected by poor landscaping practice in the study area.

Table 8 shows the response of the landscapers in the study area on the facilities and features that has evolves the poor landscaping practice in the study area, 7(23.3%) of the landscapers reported that poor source of good water has made more landscapers to loss interests in landscaping practice in the study area, poor sanitation and dumping sites has caused many areas in the study area not to have been enjoying a good landscaping services. While 10(33.3%) of the housing in the study area are not having good defecating sites and this has affected the poor landscaping features of the study area. 4(13.3%) of the landscapers responded that, improvising

Table 9. Distribution of landscapers according to their perceptions on health benefits of landscaping in the study area.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Diseases Control	5	16.7
Temperature Modification	10	33.3
Psychological Health Control	5	16.7
Environmental Beautification	10	33.3
Others	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 10. Distribution of landscapers according to what motivates them to engage in landscaping the study area.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Beautification Purposes	15	50
Aesthetic Purposes	0	0
Business and Job Opportunity	10	33.3
Environmental Modification Purposes	5	16.7
Others	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 11. Distribution of landscapers according to the impacts of environmental landscaping on their health in the study area.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Helps in Air Purification	6	20
Reduce Noise Pollution	5	16.7
Helps in Erosion Control	7	23.3
Modification of Temperature	8	26.7
Improve Water Quality	5	16.7
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

of conservable vegetation for good living has resulted in the poor landscaping feature in the study area, this implies that most landscapers in the study area do not ensure components and the growth of landscaping vegetation require constant monitoring and exchange of information with my office, as well as daily gardening maintenance which most of them do not pay priorities to.

SECTION C: Explore the perceptions of Landscapers in Sokoto South LGA towards landscaping of their environments.

Table 9 shows the landscapers responses in regard to the health impacts of landscaping on sustainable environment in the study area. 5(16.7%) of the landscapers in the study area engages in landscaping in response to disease control which can be related to the plantation of resistant varieties in controlling diseases by buying resistant varieties when they are available, also 10(33.3%) of the landscapers in the study area are into landscaping for temperature modification of the area which involves engaging sustainable landscape design approach as mitigating strategies

to modify the temperature. Also 5(16.7%) of the landscapers in the study area engages in landscaping for psychological health control by providing serene environment for relaxation and ease from depression and stress. While 10(33.3%) of the landscapers in the study area are into landscaping for environmental beautification which shows the beauty of the environment and in provision of the aesthetic values of the environmental properties.

Table 10 shows that 15 (50%) of the landscapers practices landscaping majorly for the beautification purposes, while 10 (33.3%) of the landscapers engages in landscaping majorly for business and job opportunity while 5(16.7%) of the landscapers practices landscaping majorly for environmental modification purposes, this implies that most of the respondents only engages in landscaping for the main course of beautification, others engages in landscaping for environmental modification purposes which involves to Increase Soil Health and conservation, Improving Greenery Features of the surrounding by beautifying farms, and attracting natural pest control and protect the soil from erosion and land exposure to natural disasters. Table 11, shows that 6(20%)

Table 12. Distribution of landscapers according to the major constraints they are facing for landscaping in the study area.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Pests and Diseases	6	20
High Cost of Maintenance	14	46.7
Land Tenure Security	6	20
Unavailability of Improved Varieties	4	13.3
Others	0	0
Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

of the landscapers responded that landscaping has helped in air purification, this implies that landscaping practice has helps to improve environmental quality, it has air purification and landscaping has helped in maintenance of ecological balance and the air filtration of the environment, 5(16.7%) of the landscapers responded that landscaping has helped in reducing noise pollution in the sense that the trees planted to be used to decrease the noise are quite big and hard leaves and have a dense leaf network, tall and dangling till ground and to be planted at near distance. Plant material could also be used with noise barrier walls most especially Neem Tree (*Azimantha indica*). 7(23.3%) of the landscapers reported that landscaping services has helped in control of erosion by simply adding in grasses, mulches and shrubs, landscaping has helped prevent erosion because rainwater and snowmelt will be better collected. And also to help the soil gain more stability, they have consider adding in native grasses to the space, as they will produce long roots that will be able to tie the topsoil and subsoil together such includes; *Moringa oleifera*, Earpod tree (*Enterolobium contortisiliquum*). 8(26.7%) of the landscapers reported that landscaping has helped in modification of temperature in the environment, this implies that landscaping can help control the temperature difference between the inner and outer surfaces of walls and ceilings, and thus reduce heat conduction. Also 5(16.7%) of the landscapers has reported that landscaping in the study area has helped in improving water quality by considering landscape features that will collect, store, and disperse rainfall that falls on the housing properties. This helps to minimize hard surfaces and lawn by dividing the areas of lawn and hard surfaces with native plants or gardens. And also by planting trees, shrubs and ground cover at run-off sources such as buildings, drives, and walkways.

SECTION D: To identify the constraints faced by landscapers towards landscaping in Sokoto South LGA Sokoto State.

Table 12 below shows the response of landscapers in the study area in response to the major constraints they are facing for landscaping in the study area, 6(20%) of the landscapers reported to have been having problem with pests and diseases as well as animal encroachments

such as rodents, and other livestock roaming extensively in the area, 14(46.7%) of the respondents reported that high cost of maintenance of landscaped areas has been a major constraint they are facing in landscaping practices of their areas, while 6(20%) of the landscapers reported that land security is the major constraint they are facing in landscaping of their areas this is related to landscapers living in rented houses and could not involve too much in the land space, also 4(13.3%) of the landscapers reported that the major constraint they are facing for landscaping practice in the study area is the unavailability of improved varieties of flowers, shrubs, and trees. They wish to have more of improved varieties so they can be motivated to do more, other problems related to landscaping as reported includes; poor management skills and climatic conditions of the area.

Possible Solutions to the Constraints faced by landscapers in the study area

The solutions recommended by the landscapers include; Government should prioritize policies for sustainable landscaping in the study area and also government should streamline and adopt the interests of more agriculturalists to the field of landscaping by supporting them with capitals. As well as more landscapers should be encouraged and trained for landscaping practices. Also, Awareness creation on the health benefits of landscaping in environmental sustainability should be encouraged. Good agronomic practices should be encouraged by the governments as well as possible interventions.

Testing of Hypothesis

H₁: There is significant relationship between landscaping and human health & wellbeing in the study area.

Expected Return (E) = 575/30 = 19.2. The calculated value was 38.4 while the critical value was 1.31. This result shows that the calculated value was 19.2 while the critical value was 1.31. The expected value was 19.2; from the Chi square method states that if the calculated value is more than Chi Square value in the table at 10% level of significance, then the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis which stated that:

Figure 1 showing the contribution of landscaping to human health and wellbeing in the study area.

O	E	O - E	(O-E) ²	X ² = (O-E) ² / E
15	15	0	0	0
0	15	-15	225	15
10	15	-5	25	1.7
5	15	-10	100	6.7
0	15	-15	225	15
30	15	- 45	575	38.4

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Using;

$$= \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where,

X = Chi square value

O = Observed value

E = Expected value

Landscaping contributes to human health and wellbeing in the study area is supported. Therefore this result shows that Landscaping contributes to human health and wellbeing in the study area.

CONCLUSION

An appealing landscape contributes to people’s health. From this study, it can be proven that the environment surrounding a person is of great importance to his or her stress level and health, most especially general well being. Various human activities produce pressures that alter the environment, leading to negative impacts on the human health and the environmental eco-system. But this study confirms that inhabitants could benefit from nature,

greening and landscape through direct contact with such an environment. And in many ways landscaping has helped in improvement of one’s health and wellbeing.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations were made:

1. Landscaping practice should be encouraged among landscapers in the study area, planting of trees, shrubs and hedges should be planted around residential homes to help protect the facilities and features of the environmental that will contributes to the wellbeing of the landscapers.
2. Local knowledge and resources should be highly

considered among the extension agents and landscapers to ensure cost-effectiveness and improved landscapes management among the landscapers in Sokoto South LGA, Sokoto State.

3. More effort should be put in sensitizing and creating awareness among the landscapers in the area on the health benefits of landscaping on their health and its impact to improve the wellbeing of landscapers in the study area.

4. Landscapes features in rural areas should be enhanced. Land use planning, designated floodways, reservoirs and barriers such as canals, dams, levees or floodwalls should be solidly built and maintained by agencies responsible.

5. Finally, Government should help in sensitization and training of more landscapers in the study area on how they can improve landscaping practices and diversification on the health benefits of landscaping on the well-being of landscapers in the study area.

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